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3.2 Spatial Dimension of the projects innovative approach

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, “3.2 Spatial Dimension of the Project’s Innovative Approach” investigates the spatial implications of implementing circular nutrient management solutions across the three pilot regions in Sweden (Gotland), Spain (Axarquía) and Germany (Lower Saxony and Brandenburg).

The report builds upon the prior legal and policy analyses conducted under task 3.5 “Deliverable D3.7 Scoping review” describing the status of the legislative framework which described the status quo of the legislative and regulatory framework governing circular nutrient flows. This report integrates the spatial planning considerations to assess the enabling conditions and barriers to implementation as well as potential replication of pilot technologies.

The report is structured into country-specific chapters, each providing a comprehensive spatial assessment through the study of spatial plans and identification of potential stakeholders. Each chapter starts with a contextual overview of national and regional conditions related to agriculture, sanitation and water resource availability. The stakeholder analysis identifies key actors across public private and civic domains revolving around planning, implementation and regulations.

The governance and legal framework section outlines institutional arrangements in different levels, spatial planning instruments, and regulatory environments that are relevant to circular sanitation systems.

It is followed by the study of the spatial planning in the context of land use planning, environmental planning, water and sanitation planning which are relevant for the spatial analysis. The analysis is conducted through the mapping of land use (agricultural, urban areas, environmental protection areas), nutrient sensitive areas and wastewater treatment plants, to visualise the opportunities and constraints. The relationship and proximity of different areas and its potential is also understood through the maps.

Each chapter concluded with a set of context specific recommendations aimed at supporting the scalability and integration of circular nutrient solutions into the regional planning processes

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List of Abbreviation

BSAP	Baltic Sea Action Plan
CE	Circular Economy
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EU	European Union
GVA	Gross Value Added
N&P	Nitrogen and Phosphorus
SEK	Swedish Krona
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Waste Water Treatment Plant

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1. Introduction

This deliverable is part of work package WP3 which investigates the development of circular business models, urban planning strategies, exploration of social acceptance and proposal of a legislative framework to support the implementation of circular nutrient systems in the pilot areas and beyond.

This deliverable “3.2 Spatial Dimension of the projects innovative approach” investigates the spatial implication of the implementation of the circular innovative approaches in the pilot regions- Sweden (Gotland), Spain (Axarquía), and Germany (Lower Saxony and Brandenburg). It also includes the analysis of urban spatial plans, strategic plans, urban policies and stakeholders involved. Many different policies and regulation revolving around sustainable agricultural practises, fertilisers, wastewater and water management have been compiled in Task 3.5. This study also used the analyses and legal framework of case studies from D1.4. “Blueprints from the three pilot regions”.

Firstly, the current spatial planning framework which may have influence on the circular economy (CE) solutions in the pilots are analysed. Then, the identification of the relevant stakeholders involved in the current urban planning framework and in the innovative circular solutions are focused.

The prospects of upscaling the pilot areas of Sweden, Spain and Germany are explored through a spatial analysis and other strategic approaches like mapping analysis. Data relevant to land use (agriculture, urban areas), wastewater treatment plants, water, households, protected areas/ nutrient sensitive areas are considered to illustrate thematic maps to provide an overview of the study. The pilot regions are highlighted in Fig. 1.

Examining territorial aspects, regulatory implications and governance issues can contribute to a better understanding of the environment surrounding each pilot technology. All this can be a prerequisite for the replication of the pilot technologies. The conducted analyses reveal those aspects that also require investigation in the target areas in the case of adaptation of the pilot technologies.

Figure 1 Pilot Project Locations in Sweden. Germany and Spain

2. Sweden

2.1. Background

Sweden is a country with diverse landscapes with a rich abundance of natural resources. In the recent years, however, recurrent droughts and changing precipitation patterns, have negatively impacted the nation, leading to declining ground water levels and increasing scarcity of potable water (Rosso et al., 2025). Given that a large part of land (about 2.5 million hectares) in Sweden is arable, fertiliser and water availability is a crucial concern (Jordbrukverket, 2022).

Annually, Sweden uses about 870,000 tonnes of primarily synthetic and imported fertilisers (Niléhn, 2022), while on the other hand, its nutrient rich municipal wastewater is discharged into the water bodies. This situation highlights the crucial need for recovery of nutrients from Sweden's sanitation systems (Hendriks & Langeveld, 2017). Furthermore, an estimated 700,000 small-scale sewage systems remain unconnected to the municipal wastewater treatment plants which poses a risk of ground water or surface water pollution as well as eutrophication (SwAM, 2021)

As in other pilot regions, there are still social and cultural reservations in the use of human excreta for agricultural purposes in Sweden as well, often due to concerns about hazardous substances. This has led to a slow exchange of information and insufficient dialogues between farmers and other stakeholders about circular nutrient innovations (Parfitt, 2023).

Nonetheless, there has been a progress in Sweden's use of sludge in recent years, with about 34% of treated sewage sludge reused in farming. This shift has been supported by Revaq's certification which promotes safer wastewater treatment practices and fertilisers derived from sludge (SOU, 2020). Even then, the farmers in Sweden are yet to be more informed about these initiations that allow the use of urine and sludge in conventional agriculture (Parfitt, 2023).

The pilot region of Gotland is an island located in the Baltic Sea. In December 2024, the population in the island was about 61,029 while in the peak touristic season, about 2 million tourists are registered in the hotels in addition to the motor homes. This also escalates the waste and water problem in Gotland. Agriculture takes up a large share, with about 35 % of the islands surface covered in farmland. Only about 60% of its population connected to the municipal water network as compared to the national average of 87% (SCB, 2016). A large share of residents (40%) living in small communities or the countryside continue to rely upon private wells for their water. The local cement plant operates on a large water supply system based on reservoirs while farms typically rely on wells for household water and on-farm reservoirs for irrigation and livestock production. Many accounts of drought have also been experienced in the region which makes the pilot demonstration even more relevant.

In the pilot project, urine that is collected from events like music festivals, is the main source of fertiliser, which is dried and transformed into pellets and used to grow barley. This is ultimately brewed into beer and commercially sold. The programme aims to collect 150m³ of urine by the end of the project to help close the nutrient loop in the agricultural industry (P2Green, 2025).

The following chapters further explains the potential of upscaling the project in Gotland.

2.2. Stakeholders

The main stakeholders of the pilot project in Gotland are Touch Down, a local toilet rental company, Gottlands Bryggeri, a local beer brewery and the Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU) and Sanitation 360. For the pilot region, the European Union (EU) funds comprise 70% of the total costs and 30% from the local brewery.

Figure 2 Stakeholders of Gotland's pilot project

Other potential stakeholders have also been identified, that may further support the mission of the project through their diverse approaches and interests. They are-

- Water Wise Society
- Helsinki Commission (HELCOM)
- Gotland Hopespot
- LEADER Approach
- Baltic Stewardship Initiative

- Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP)
- CINURGY
- Swedish Agency Marine and Water Management (SwAM)
- Oslo and Paris Conventions (OSPAR Commission)
- Wastewater Treatment Plants in Gotland

They are further described in brief in Chapter 2.6. Spatial / Rural Development Support

2.3. Governance levels in spatial context

In general, Sweden operates under a parliamentary democracy and a constitutional monarchy, where the monarch is the ceremonial head of the state while the political power is exercised by the elected representatives. The state administration is divided into 21 counties (Län) which is governed by County Administration Board appointed by the national government while the regional council is elected by the residents. It is further divided into 290 municipalities (Kommuner) which are also elected by the locals. (Government Offices of Sweden, 2015). The responsible agencies, their planning instruments and their tasks are explained in table 1.

Table 1:: The Swedish Planning System (own, reproduced from (Boverket, 2023, Schmitt,2023)

Government level/ Actor	Role	Legal Foundations	Planning Instruments		Function
National	Spatial planning at national level	The Planning and Building Act (PBL), The Environmental Code, Swedish Environmental Protection Agency	Land Use Planning	The National Board of housing, building and planning	principles of comprehensive spatial planning and national interests like environmental protection and infrastructure development
Regional Counties(Län)	Spatial planning at regional or county level	Spatial planning Act and Land planning legislation	Regional Development Programs (RUP)	a spatial structure plan a special and sectoral sub-plans	County Councils (<i>Landsting</i>) along with county administrative board (<i>Länsstyrelsen</i>) aims of comprehensive spatial planning Certain regions like Stockholm, Skane and Halland have established regional plans to address cross municipality issues
Municipalities (Kommuner)	Urban land use planning	Federal building code	Comprehensive Plan (<i>Översiktsplan</i>)	Detailed Development	Land use and building regulation for specific areas

Plan (<i>Detaljplan</i>)	Legally responsible for water supply, waste disposal systems, collection of urine
Building Permissions, Supervision and Control	Issue of building permits according to other legislations,

2.4. Spatial Planning

a. Land use planning

The Swedish Parliament is the main governing office that has prioritised the environment and climate through its 16 environmental quality objectives dealing with water, agricultural and ecology. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency and County Administration Board are responsible for land use planning by defining building codes, zoning, designating protected areas and controlling sectoral policies. The Swedish Agricultural Agency also plays a pivotal role in designating agricultural and restrictive areas in the country (Boverket, 2023).

In the regional level, the County Councils handle the intermediary level of governance and are guided by the regional development program to lead different strategies for regional development. They are legally responsible for water supply, sewerage collection and waste disposal. The counties are further divided into municipalities (Boverket, 2023). The local government is solely responsible for the collection of urine.

Gotland is a special case being a region/county and municipality at the same time. The municipality of Gotland undertakes the local planning, prepares comprehensive plans and issues building permits as well as provide technical infrastructure for land development. Regional and comprehensive plans (*översiktsplan*) are made based on planning and building acts and are also supported by the action plans from Our Gotland 2040 (Schmitt, 2023).

b. Environmental planning

There are many counts of Swedish Nature Conservation and Water protection areas which could be an enabling factor to promote sustainable agriculture, reduce water and soil pollution with circular nutrient solutions. The national environmental objectives are designated to different agencies like Swedish Agency Marine and Water Management (SwAM), whose objectives are Zero Eutrophication, Flourishing Lakes and Streams, and A Balanced Marine Environment, Flourishing Coastal Areas and Archipelagos (SwAM, 2021).

There are about 11 Nature reserve area and Natura 2000 sites in Gotland which are protected by law. Most of the water sensitive areas are in the coasts and around lakes. The protection of the latter is critical for maintaining surface water quality. The

Environmental Protection Office for Gotland is responsible for the protection and monitoring of these areas. Similarly, The Swedish Strategy for lakes and water courses and the Swedish Agency Marine and Environment strategy provide detailed plans for protection of sensitive water areas.

Sweden's Agricultural Agency maps and analyses both Sweden's existing fertiliser production capacity as well as the potential for domestic fertiliser production and also identified initiatives that can support domestic and circular fertiliser production (Parfitt, 2023). The Swedish Meteorological Hydrological Institute (SMHI) provides climate reports of each county and has pushed for regional water supply plans to be developed by every region. It provides essential and accurate data for establishing protection zones and safety regulations for surface water sources to safeguard drinking water areas.

Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) is one of the strategic programmes that aims to improve the status of the sea, with measures to reduce the nutrients inputs in the sea, enhance the biodiversity and incorporate innovative management approaches as well as updated scientific knowledge into strategic policy implementation (HELCOM, 2021).

Similarly, Gotland Rural Development Programme receives funding from various EU sources including the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), focuses on restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry (Region Gotland, 2021).

In addition, the climate objectives in the regional development strategy (RDS), called *Vårt Gotland 2040* or 'Our Gotland 2040' have a broader focus on reducing carbon emissions, biodiversity and grasslands and capacity building for sustainable production and conservation of water resources as well as promotion of innovation and renewal. Food security is also one of the chief focuses which is linked to sustainable agriculture and use of fertilisers. The future aspects include regional self-sufficiency, Although the interpretation of the plans depends on the decisions of the permitting agencies (Region Gotland, 2025).

Gotland Regional Development Plan plans to achieve environment and economic sustainability by supporting the development of urban and agricultural areas Creating an environment for business owners, inhabitants and tourism is also on their agenda. The plan envisions creating service points to further enhance the connection between rural and urban (Region Gotland, 2025).

c. Water and Sanitation Planning

The national government plans on the legal basis of the Environmental Code while The Environmental Protection Agency guide the construction of sealed septic tanks dug toilets and monitors and controls the grey water treatment. Gotland Regional Development plan goes through different levels of governance for the collective approach to sustainable water and waste management

As mentioned before, the region of Gotland is solely responsible for the water supply and sanitation systems. The wastewater is managed through region-owned treatment facilities in most settlements and through septic systems on farms and other isolated homes. In addition, civil society is also playing a role in providing supplemental sewage treatment capacity in some smaller communities that are then used for irrigation purposes.

Gotland municipality's Water and Waste strategy published in 2019, outlines a comprehensive and inclusive plan to monitor projects related to it. To facilitate effective project implementation, working groups and advisory roles were appointed to help the stakeholders be part of the development plan. It also included actions to improve the existing facilities as well as development of new water treatment plants where needed.

Vårt Gotland 2040 also reinforces that the reduction of the load on central WWTPs is one of the crucial steps that resonate with their commitments and emphasizes on implementing decentralized wastewater treatment systems and improving facilities. The whole region of Gotland has been designated as a nitrate sensitive area as illustrated in Fig.3. Therefore, such measures are crucial for the island.

There are 25 different water treatment plants for the water supply on Gotland, of which 2 are desalination plants, 2 surface water plants, 1 treats water from a former stone quarry and the rest are groundwater treatment plants. Water is collected from reservoirs for irrigation and some from desalination plants. Regarding clean water, it aims to increase the access to clean water and also provides strategies for wetland protection and other environmental protection plans (Region Gotland, 2025). However, there has not been any mention of economic instruments like pricing and metering the water usage.

Figure 3 Dedicated nitrate sensitive areas of pilot area (own editing based on data from the GeoPortal, Lantmäteriet, 2024)

The treated water is supplied by regional government-owned entities. In Gotland, there are 4 biological wastewater treatment plants with N&P removal in Gotland (WISE, 2023). The distribution of these WWTPs is illustrated in Fig. 4, three of the WWTPs are located near the coasts while the facility in Hemse is amidst the city. ()

Table 2 Wastewater treatment plants on Gotland and their capacity (WISE,2023)

Location of Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTP)	Capacity in person equivalent (p.e)
Slite	8,000
Visby	60,000
Hemse	2,100
Klintehamns	10,000

The WWTP in Klintehamns have improved facilities than the others. In case of increase in the population, the WWTP would have to expand which could be cost intensive and time consuming (Naturvårdsverket, 2022).

Figure 4 Urban wastewater treatment plants and agricultural land in Gotland (Source GeoPortal, Lantmäteriet, 2024), edited by authors)

There are about 40,000 houses with decentralised wastewater systems in Sweden with about 14,000 houses located in Gotland, offering opportunities for decentralised sanitation projects (Senecal, 2024).

There is a close proximity between the WWTPs and large settlements as well as the agricultural areas as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 Urban areas, protected areas, water bodies and agricultural land in Gotland (Source GeoPortal, Lantmäteriet, 2024, edited by authors)

2.5. Policy and Regulations

To support sustainable agriculture and regulate the water use and sanitation systems, Sweden has adopted many policies over the years which show their openness and willingness to take necessary steps to whether meet the climate goals or to protect the local environment. They are explained below in the categories of incentives, mobilization, awareness and regulations.

Incentives

The municipalities who apply to the government to solve local issues were entrusted with 45 million Swedish Krona (SEK). Solely for the advancement for the WWTP, approximately 250 million SEK was allocated from 2018-2020, and the initiative has been extended to 2021 and 2022 to further reduce emissions of pharmaceutical residues and increase the possibilities for reuse of wastewater. (Lindqvist & Sköld, 2023).

From 2017 to 2021, the Swedish government has increased the appropriation for measures to the marine and aquatic environment by 78%, to almost 1.4 billion SEK (Lindqvist & Sköld, 2023).

In efforts to promoting the use of sustainable agriculture, use of organic fertilisers, Sweden's CAP strategic plan includes economic incentives and action plans to upscaling organic fertilisers. It planned a total of 806 million SEK is to be paid to the farmers to promote sustainable agricultural practices in areas where farming conditions were poor. About 14,000 farmers planned to receive support for livestock production for local food security and promotion and profitability of the sector (Lindqvist & Sköld, 2023).

About 30% of the EUs financial contribution was allocated to support environmental and climate objectives, focused on reducing carbon emissions, improving biodiversity and grasslands as well as fostering capacity building for sustainable production. Along with it, the farmers have the chance to get additional funding if they are dedicated towards organic farming (Farm Europe, 2022).

The Climate Leap provide subsidies and fundings for climate related investments within agricultural sector (Pareliussen & Purwin, 2023) while The Industrial Leap, focused on supporting emissions reduction in industries. Since, agriculture is one of the largest non-ETS emission sources in Sweden, it is also in its radar (Region Gotland, 2025);(Krisinformation, 2023)

There are also national direct payments that are planned to accelerate climate targets. They are given to the farmers to adopt potentially climate friendly practices, but the payments are not linked to achieving specific environmental outcomes (Region Gotland, 2025). Precision agriculture is a management approach that uses data and technology to optimise resource use and improvement of crop production. The farmers who opt these approaches are also compensated for one year. One of the conditions is that the arable land must be in nitrate sensitive area and Gotland is mapped as one.

Mobilization

A national-funded testbed is under development in southern Gotland and has been trying to address the current challenges with various strategies and technologies. An important and critical part of the testbed project is communication and engagement activities with local stakeholders, such as farmers and citizens. This project seeks for collaboration with other projects that could help mitigate the water problems in Gotland (IVL,2025).

Awareness

Gotland's comprehensive water and waste plan 2019, emphasized on transparency with residents by providing maps and updates on project developments. The plan involves establishing working groups to assist stakeholders in the development process, improving existing facilities, and potentially constructing new treatment plants (Länsstyrelsen Gotlands län, 2025).

Regulations

Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, the Swedish Consumer Agency and Swedish Chemicals Agency who have urged the consumers to be more mindful towards shopping as a large amount of water is required just to produce one single piece of clothing. This has had repercussions in the way clothing companies have started to produce clothes with less water and advertised it being more environment friendly (SIWI, 2014)

Gotland has since passed a watering ban, limiting the use of water during peak tourist seasons (Svergesradio, 2016).

Sweden currently invests 227 euros per citizen per year for new collecting and treatment infrastructure, as well as for the renewal of ageing infrastructure. This is above the EU average of 41 euros per citizen every year. (WISE, 2023)

2.6. Spatial/ Rural Development Support

The following organisations were identified as potential stakeholders for the pilot region as a whole due to the similarity in their objectives with the project, like preventing eutrophication and pollution in the ocean, protection of the local resources and the environment as well as fostering of sustainable communities.

Gotland Hopespot

Mission Blue, ocean conservation nonprofit, has named Gotland a Hope Spot to bring ocean awareness to the public through hands-on and digital educational programs for children and youth (Gotland Hope Spot, 2023).

Leader Approach

Capacity building is also one of the main agendas to educate farmers about the nitrogen and carbon cycle on the farm. Similarly, it also focused on strengthening local communities through the LEADER approach bringing together all the stakeholders. Similarly, young farmers are also encouraged through incentives during their start up phases and enabling necessary investment and support.

Water Wise Society

Water Wise Societies have been fostering Sweden's transition towards sustainable water keeping in mind the social, environmental and economic aspects. It also works to help policy makers to support water conservation and sustainable practises at different levels.

A yearly budget of about 10 million euros is allocated for different organisations, institutions, companies that are interested to work in the field of water-efficient farming practises and prevention of eutrophication through different technologies and decentralised solutions along with the wastewater reuse for irrigation and other purposes. It also encourages community engagement in sustainable water practises.

HELCOM

HELCOM Commission is the governing body of the *Convention on the protection of the Baltic Sea Area*, and its main objective is to protect the marine sphere of the Baltic Sea from imminent environment threats. It is an intergovernmental platform where Sweden is also one of the members and mainly monitors the environment in the Baltic Sea through data collection and mainly addresses eutrophication, agriculture and wastewater managements.

Sweden reduces nutrient runoff through HELCOM's Nutrient Reduction Action Program (BSAP) by adopting sustainable farming practises. Sweden must also follow the HELCOM standards to improve the wastewater treatment and reduce nutrient discharge into the water bodies. Its Eutrophication Program also supports Sweden in monitoring and reducing nutrient pollution and instead promotes reusing wastewater as a circular economy approach. HELCOM also facilitates in knowledge transfer on best practises and technological innovations to combat eutrophication.

Other initiatives and actors like *Baltic Stewardship Initiative and CINURGY* also have the collective aim of promoting sustainable agricultural practises and are intertwined in the whole food chain.

2.7. Spatial Analysis and Recommendation

Public Engagement and Awareness

The municipalities and the residents can also play a vital role in upscaling the resource-oriented sanitation approaches. Initiatives like Gotland's beer production with barley that was grown with the support of urine-based fertilisers could be scaled to reach broader markets, leveraging economies of scale and public awareness campaigns. Strategies can include mapping regional breweries, calculating the amount of manure or wastewater required to irrigate farmlands and visualising these demands and supply to raise awareness. Urine-based fertilizers present a promising, safe, and eco-friendly alternative to traditional fertilizers. The bio-based fertiliser regulations in the European Union which is still in draft form may accelerate such initiatives

Tackling eutrophication through resource-oriented sanitation

As discussed, eutrophication poses significant environmental and financial burdens due to algae removal costs and protecting these lakes through resource-oriented sanitation seem like a better alternative, especially as urban wastewater management costs continue to rise. Prioritizing intervention areas by mapping affected lakes and water bodies could streamline efforts. By centralizing a pilot project around treatment plants and involving nearby households can serve as a model. Public acceptance surveys and collaborations with farmers could further enhance the scalability and efficiency of nutrient recycling systems.

Decentralised sanitation systems for urban areas

Since, connecting wastewater systems in urban areas is rather expensive, decentralised sanitation systems can be a practical alternative. Identifying and prioritising these housing units for separate or dry toilets could address these challenges. Urine diverting toilets can also be provided in low prices or for free of charge, these types of incentives can be introduced to ease the transitions. This also applies to new settlements as increasing the capacity and efficiency of WWTP can be equally challenging and cost intensive. Since there is a water scarcity in Gotland, this can be an opportunity to engage stakeholders such as municipal authorities and water infrastructure department, that could yield sustainable and localised solutions. . The possible intervention areas in Uppsala, Visby as well as the public toilets can be studied in the next steps.

Event based and large-scale collection strategies

A promising strategy for resource-oriented sanitation is collecting urine from event toilets, using projections to estimate annual urine resources. For these projects to succeed, strong public-private partnerships will be essential to secure adequate infrastructure, ensure public support, and optimize nutrient recycling on a large scale.

It was noted that there were not enough toilet provisions in the public spaces. Therefore, resource-oriented sanitation can be integrated with the installation of new public toilets to address the dual issues simultaneously.

Engagement of farmers and addressing logistics

With the surveys to understand the acceptance of the inhabitants for the urine separation, there can be an estimate about the amount of urine that can be collected from each household. It is ideal to have the farmers also in the loop so that there can be a contract with the farmers as well as farmland analysis can be done to juxtapose the number of households and the proximity of plants and farms to minimise logistic challenges.

Bridging Administrative gaps

One significant challenge is the divided administration in urban areas where water and waste are considered as two different departments which have little to no coordination

with each other. Overcoming these gaps and strengthening collaborations will be critical to implement cohesive and effective resource-oriented sanitation solution

3. Spain

3.1. Background

Spanish agriculture is characterised by a high contribution to the country's economy, with the primary sector accounting for 2.9% of the country's economy (total GVA). Agriculture provides a livelihood for 800,000 farmers in the country (CAP, 2023). Half of the country's territory is under agricultural cultivation. The proportion of irrigated areas is significant (15% of the agricultural land (World Bank, 2021), and the demand for irrigation water is increasing year by year (Hurtado et al. 2024).

The Spanish pilot region, Axarquía is a semi-arid region in southern Spain that has seen significant population growth over the past 25 years, as well as an economic boom due to the increasing number of tourists arriving at the coast and the expansion of irrigated, export-oriented subtropical crops. Agricultural farms are gradually turning to water-intensive crops in order to be more profitable, which also increases water demand. The combination of these factors has led to a chronic structural water scarcity situation, exacerbated by long and extreme droughts. As a result, the only reservoir in the microregion has reached historically low levels and there are other signs of overexploitation of groundwater resources (Hurtado et al. 2024).

Figure 6 The agricultural area of Axarquía (Edited by authors based on data from the GeoPortal, 2025)

The region's water crisis is affecting citizens (interruptions in urban water supply), farmers (crop and yield losses) and the environment (reduced water resources). The different levels of authorities have responded with supply-side measures, including the incorporation of reclaimed wastewater into irrigation systems and the planning of the construction of desalination infrastructure in the region. At the same time, to guarantee sustainability, demand control and proper management are also necessary, which is facilitated, for example, by preparing a regional irrigation strategy and maximizing the amount of water available for irrigation (Hurtado et al. 2024).

Figure 7 The dedicated irrigation area of Axarquía (Edited by Authors based on data from the GeoPortal, 2025)

The case study area, Axarquía municipality (in Andalusia Autonomous Region) integrates water reclamation technology with a smart irrigation system. Treated wastewater from the municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in Algarrobo settlement undergoes additional purification at a water reclamation facility, where disc filtration and ozone disinfection remove pathogens and contaminants. This advanced treatment process transforms wastewater into a nutrient-rich effluent, capable of producing 3,650 m³ of reclaimed water annually. The reclaimed water is then used to fertigate avocado and mango crops. If necessary, it can be supplemented with mineral fertilizers or diluted with local water, all managed by an innovative smart fertigation tool (the entire region is classified as a nitrate-sensitive area). The smart fertigation tool monitors key nutrients and soil elements that influence crop development, promoting a sustainable and circular approach to nutrient and water resource management in the region.

Figure 8 The wastewater treatment and irrigation infrastructure of Algarrobo's WWT area (Edited by authors based on data from the GeoPortal, 2025)

3.2. Stakeholders

Without the involvement and continuous information of identified stakeholders, the implementation of the pilot project or its successful replication is unimaginable.

The *main identified stakeholders* of this pilot project are: *AXARAGUA* public operator of the Algarrobo municipal wastewater treatment plant, *BIOAZUL* technology provider for wastewater reclamation, *TROPS* farmers' cooperative, crop management and technical advisor for fertigation, *Agualytics* software developer of the Smart Fertigation Tool, and *CETAQUA*, which is the scientific partner for the analysis of the collected data.

Figure 9 Stakeholders and processes of Spanish pilot project (P2GreenN, 2025)

Other *potential stakeholders* have also been identified. Actors who can play a role in the use of the technology (regulation, permits, planning) or dissemination (regulation, users, utilities), but also those who can help shape the attitudes of consumers/users (green, climate organizations, community or civil society organizations).

These are:

- National government
- Regulators, authorities
- Regional and local governments
- Irrigation communities
- Farmers
- LEADER Action Groups
- Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)
- Spanish Association of Desalination and Reuse (AEDYR)
- Spanish Association for Sustainable Water Reuse (ASERSA)
- National Federation of Irrigation Communities of Spain (FENACORE)
- EIP-AGRI Operational Groups
- Universities, research centres
- Innovators, technology owners

Public participation is an integral part of the spatial planning process in Spain both the development and land use planning types. Citizens, stakeholders, and interest groups have the opportunity to participate in public consultations, hearings, and decision-making processes to provide input on planning policies and projects that affect their communities.

3.3. Governance levels in spatial context

Spain is typically defined as a quasi-federal state with four levels of government. According to the EUROSTAT (2024) classification, the country consists of the national government, 17 autonomous communities, 50 provinces, and 8,132 municipalities.

Table 3 The Spanish Planning System (Edited by authors based on (OECD, 2017))

Government Level / Actor	Role	Legal Foundations	Planning	Function
State Government (Estado)	General coordination, national infrastructure (e.g., water), environmental protection, safeguarding national interests.	Law on Land Use Planning and Urban Development (Ley de Ordenación del Territorio y Urbanismo, LOTU)		à -national government prepares framework legislation - environmental planning
Community (Comunidades Autónomas) Autonomous	Main authority for territorial planning; develops regional strategies and regulatory frameworks.	-Statute of Autonomy for Andalusia Law 7/2021 on Sustainable Territorial Development of Andalusia (LISTA) -Law 9/2010 on Water in Andalusia	-Territorial Planning Plans -Sectoral and Regional Plans -Plan for the Protection of the Coastal Corridor of Andalusia	- spatial plans for region - Territorial Plan of the Region - regional development plans -sustainable development strategies- environmental plans
Provincial Level (Diputaciones Provinciales)	Coordination among small municipalities, technical assistance. Role varies across autonomous communities.	General administrative laws (e.g., Law 7/1985)	Provincial coordination documents, technical recommendations	-they have a supporting and coordinating role, and may also issue recommendations

Local Authorities (Municipalities - Ayuntamientos)	Urban planning, building and land use planning regulations, local development initiatives.	-General Urban Development Plan (Plan General de Ordenación Urbana - PGOU) - Detailed Plans (Plan Parcial, Plan Especial) - Special zoning regulations	- urban master plans (land use and development) -partial plans (for a given territory)
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The pilot project area is the town of *Algarrobo*, located in the comarca of Axarquía, within the province of Málaga, which is part of the autonomous community of Andalusia. Besides Algarrobo, the comarca of Axarquía includes 31 other municipalities. Municipalities are responsible for local governance and the provision of a wide range of public services to residents.

Figure 10 The territorial scope of Spanish pilot project (Edited by authors based on data from the GeoPortal, 2025)

As a historical region, *Andalusia* enjoys extensive autonomy, including its own parliament, regional government, and legislative assembly. The division of responsibilities among Spain's autonomous communities, provinces, and municipalities is outlined in the Spanish Constitution and subsequent legislation, which define their respective powers and duties.

Spatial plans, land use plans and development plans follow administrative boundaries at different levels of government. However, there are also special planning zones that differ from these administrative boundaries.

The Costa del Sol is the Andalusian coastal region where Axarquía is located. In Spain, special legislation applies to *coastal zones*, in line with which special plans have been prepared for the coastal areas (i.e. Malaga) of Andalusia, for example to eliminate the effects of climate change.

In Spain, water management regions are defined, where water supply needs to be managed together, considering the combination of catchment areas and natural/built reservoirs and installed desalination plants. Within Andalusia also *water authorities* operate for these designated water basin regions. The water basin authority that is responsible for the pilot test site is Mediterranean Basin. The water basin authority allocates irrigation water (concession) rights based on the regional government's *hydrological plan*.

Figure 11 Spanish River Basin Districts (Source: ClientEarth, 2024)

Irrigation communities integrate agricultural actors within a catchment area that have declared water use needs. Water use plans and annual prior authorisations are carried out by the water basin authorities (within the water management regions, but for each catchment area) using supply-side planning, i.e. they estimate how much water resources may remain for irrigation after the effects of climate change, weather forecasts and the needs of primary consumers have been met.

Hundreds of irrigation areas exist in Andalusia, administered by so called irrigation communities (Comunidades de Regantes). Most of the irrigation communities are private and show a wide variety in size, water availability, and crops cultivated. Many of these irrigation communities share elements of the technical infrastructure of their water management systems, like tunnels for tapping groundwater or widely distributed channels of irrigation networks. Rotation based water allocation is a common feature. In some cases, additional water rights can be bought from the irrigation community by its members during regular auctions (Isselhort et al., 2018).

The administrative area of *Algarrobo* belongs to different catchment areas and authorities, the functional catchment areas do not fit into administrative boundaries and there are also several water and wastewater treatment plants operating in the area with different territorial scope.

The provision of *public water and wastewater services* is the responsibility of local governments. Although municipalities are the owners of water supply and sewerage services, the regulation allows for the use of different forms of service provision (municipal services, public companies, concessions to the private sector, mixed companies, which represent a one-stop public-private partnership) (Blue Community, 2025).

3.4. Spatial Planning

a. Land use planning

The utilities required for this pilot project must have a building permit, which must comply with the relevant local/regional land use plans. The location of the necessary infrastructure must be designated in the land use plans.

The national government has important powers in policy fields related to spatial planning. However, it has no authority to prepare a general national spatial plan (CoR, 2018). The central government prepares sectoral plans for example related to transport and energy, environment, infrastructure, solid waste, etc.

Andalusia's *regional government plays a significant role in spatial planning*, as the autonomous region has the authority to create regional development plans (Planes de Ordenación Territorial) that guide land use and development within its territory.

Municipalities' tasks include urban planning (Planes Urbanísticos), that regulate land use and zoning within their jurisdictions. These plans establish guidelines for urban growth, designate areas for residential, commercial, industrial, and recreational use, and set standards for building construction and design. The municipalities also prepare *development plans* for their own administrative areas.

b. Water scarcity management

Water scarcity is a huge challenge in Spain. The technology implemented in this pilot project is an important and replicable response to water scarcity.

The construction of irrigation infrastructure is managed in Spain through several legal and regulatory documents, including the *National Irrigation Plan* (Plan Nacional de Regadíos), which sets out the country's priorities in the development of irrigation infrastructure. This aims to ensure sustainable water use and improve agricultural productivity, especially in water-scarce regions (MAPA, 2002).

Aware of the importance and seriousness of these challenges, the central government has accepted the *River Basin Management Plans* (2022-2027). Before this, each river basin authority (or the authority designated for planning) prepared its own plan. They contemplate in a more extensive and explicit way the risk of climate change and the need for the management of water resources to adapt to this risk, in order to increase water security and the resilience of systems (MITERD, 2022). In these water management plans; water authorities must also address various protected areas (such as nitrate-sensitive areas).

Figure 12 Dedicated nitrate sensitive areas of pilot area (Edited by authors based on data from the GeoPortal, 2025)

As a kind of implementation tool, the central government has drawn up the *National Plan for Wastewater Treatment, Sanitation, Efficiency, Savings and Reuse* (DSEAR Plan). This DSEAR Plan incorporates improved procedures and working methodologies that are well aligned with the principles of the ecological transition and the demographic challenge (DSEAR Plan, 2021). The main elements of this plan are (MITERD, 2022):

- Promote sanitation and Wastewater Treatment actions in urban settlements
- Incorporate the latest innovations and technological advances into the treatment facilities
- Promote specific action plans for small and medium-sized urban settlements, which have greater difficulty in complying with regulatory requirements
- Establish measures to reduce plastic pollution,
- Promote and develop measures for the reuse of treated wastewater, especially in agriculture and in those territories that present the greatest water imbalances.

Andalusia is particularly exposed to problems caused by drought and water scarcity. The regional government adopted a drought plan and some initiatives that seek not only immediate solutions, but also long-term sustainable strategies to ensure the availability

of water resources for future generations. *Drought Plus Strategy* aims to improve water supply in areas affected by drought, promote water saving and mitigate its economic, social and environmental impacts. Planned actions range from the use of portable desalination plants to improvements in water treatment infrastructure and the expansion of water resources (reclaimed water, transport water by ships) (Junta de Andalucía, 2023).

The Andalusian regional government in 2024 approved the first *Non-Conventional Water Resources Strategy*. This Strategy aims to reach 180 hm³ of reclaimed water in the region (for agricultural, environmental and urban use), which will turn Andalusia into the autonomous region that reclaims the most wastewater in Spain. Investments are mainly related to the upgrade of existing WWTPs in the region (Junta de Andalucía, 2024a).

Moreover, a specific plan, the “*Plan Parra*”, for water reclamation and reuse in agriculture has been launched in 2024 by the Regional Government of Andalusia. The Government plans to mobilize funds to build the necessary pipelines to transport reclaimed water from tertiary treatments of different Andalusian WWTPs to the infrastructure of the irrigation communities (Junta de Andalucía, 2024b).

c. Circular water use

Water recovery is a possible and important direction for circular economy solutions in Spain, given the economic weight of the agricultural sector and the high proportion of irrigated areas.

The *Spanish Circular Economy Strategy* sets a series of quantitative objectives to be achieved by 2030, among which is a 10% improvement in efficiency in water use. Specifically, and regarding irrigation, the aforementioned document states that “modernization projects will be ranked in accordance with hydrological planning criteria in which surface or groundwater is to be replaced by reclaimed water, within the framework of a balanced, sustainable and orderly territorial development of our rural areas” (MITERD, 2022).

The *Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy* and the connected Action Plan addresses the promotion of water regeneration through water reuse (EABC, 2018). The strategy includes collaboration with public and private sectors to invest in technology and infrastructure for reclaimed water, alongside fostering community acceptance and the adoption of sustainable irrigation practices. The strategy reflects Andalusia’s intention to transition toward a more circular and sustainable economy that optimally uses available resources, with reclaimed water serving as a critical tool for sustainable agriculture and environmental management.

d. Environmental planning

The latest *Andalusian Environment Plan 2030* (PMA, 2022) aims to integrate and guide the region's environmental policy comprehensively. This plan focuses on sustainable

development, climate change adaptation, and resource management across multiple areas, including treated wastewater. The plan supports the use of treated wastewater as part of its circular economy efforts.

The aim of *Andalusian Environmental Framework Strategy* (EMMA, 2021) to summarize the main lines of action of the Andalusian government's environmental policy up to 2030. The framework strategy addresses relevant thematic areas within the Sustainable water management actions, such as the maintenance of water balance and guarantee of water supply, or support of non-conventional water sources.

The *Andalusian Sustainable Development Strategy* (2018) defines regional action lines and measures in areas considered strategic for sustainable development (Quintanilla Cabañero et al. 2023). The issue of water is included in both the strategic areas of natural resources and environmental quality (effective water management, pollution reduction and the use of treated wastewater are among the dedicated objectives).

The *Andalusian Climate Action Plan* (2021) is a general strategic planning instrument for the fight against climate change. The water specific four strategic lines within this document are: the knowledge, the integration of water resources in planning, the creation of work groups and the maintenance of the good condition of the waters. According to flood prevention the plan dedicates three strategic lines that address the creation of work groups, the integration of climate change into the Flood Risk Management Plan and the adaptation of flood risk areas (EMMA, 2021).

3.5. Spatial Analysis and recommendation

Approximately 80% of the urban wastewater generated in the Axarquía comarca is treated and reused today, and about 13.5 hm³/year of reclaimed water have been introduced in the system to date (Hurtado, 2024). By expanding the investigated pilot technology, this *volume could increase (the aim is 19.14 hm³/year* (Junta de Andalucía, 2023)) and the possibility of customising irrigation use of *reclaimed water* of the pilot technology, could further enhance the efficient water management of the Andalusia region. *The technology could also be of help in regions facing similar water resource management challenges as in Spain.*

The piloted technology *facilitates the recycling of useful nutrients* flowing through WWTPs for agricultural use, which helps prevent the organic loading of living waters and the loss of valuable components along traditional WWTP processes.

In the coastal areas of La Axarquía, including Algarrobo, the existing sewage infrastructure faces critical challenges. One of the key issues reported is *seawater intrusion into the sewage network*, which leads to high salinity levels in the collected wastewater. This problem has several negative implications, which reduce efficiency of wastewater treatment plants. Given that the issue affects multiple municipalities in the coastal zone of La Axarquía, a regional approach is essential. *Regional Wastewater*

Infrastructure Development Plan could help in the comprehensive diagnosis of the problem and the total affected coastal area, the identification of common intervention directions and the allocation of development resources for successful joint action.

Irrigation and water reclamation also require huge investments, both in maintaining and adapting existing infrastructures to the challenges of climate change and in implementing new investments. In Andalusia, government actors are making strong commitments in this area, but in order to disseminate pilot technology, the participation of private capital is also essential to find sustainable business models. Since the use of treated wastewater creates positive externalities by reducing pollution and the burden on living waters, the *government involvement would be necessary to make a spatial expansion*.

There is a need of the creation an *Integrated Water User Communities* (Hurtado, 2024) that will bring together representatives from the three main groups of groundwater users in the water basin: the main irrigator communities in the region, and Axaragua (the confederation of local public supply operators and municipalities), and the representatives of other water users (industrial users, households, touristic service providers etc.). A condition for sustainable water resource management would be the creation of sustainable demand, which can only be guaranteed by a joint, consensual decision of the group of water consumers.

National/regional plans are also being developed in Spain in the areas of water use, irrigation and non-conventional water supply. However, a *regional irrigation potential plan* based on irrigation potential assessments would also be needed, which would be able to coordinate the demand and supply sides (either through regulation or incentives) of water.

4. Germany

4.1. Background

In 2020, 262,800 agricultural businesses in Germany farmed around half of the country's land area. The utilised agricultural area was around 16.6 million hectares. Of the utilised agricultural area, 70.3% was arable land, 28.5% permanent grassland and 1.2% permanent crops. Cereals are the most important crop in Germany with winter wheat remaining the most important crop, accounting for 23.7% of the total arable area (BMEL, 2022). In 2022 around 554,000 hectares, which are around 3.3 % of the agriculturally utilised open land in Germany, were irrigated. This means that the irrigated area was almost half (+49 % or +181,300 hectares) larger in 2022, a year with very low precipitation, than in 2009 (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2024).

Germany's current sanitation system relies on waterborne sewer networks and centralized wastewater and stormwater treatment. While this system ensures high hygiene standards, it has notable drawbacks, including low resource efficiency, high investment and operational costs, rising wastewater fees, and significant expenses for

infrastructure maintenance and refurbishment. Wastewater treatment plants in Germany invest substantial effort and resources in removing nitrogen and phosphorus, even though these nutrients could be repurposed as fertilizers. However, there are no clear legal frameworks for using fertilizers derived from human waste. Such products can currently only be utilized for research under specific exemptions in fertilizer regulations or classified as secondary resources under recycling laws. With growing urbanization and increasing population density, decentralized sanitation systems are becoming increasingly relevant across many German states. These systems also offer viable solutions for new settlements and buildings undergoing renovation, where connecting to the existing sewage network would be costly (DWA, 2010).

The German pilot aims to contribute to further establish decentralized sanitation solutions and to produce safe fertilisers based on urine and faeces. The pilot region is called North German Plain and actually is located in two regions. The two facilities of the German pilot regions are located in the federal states of Lower Saxony (fecal composting) and Brandenburg (urine treatment). Both are agricultural states and relatively less densely populated with 165 P/km² and 85 P/km² respectively.

In the German pilot North German Plain, fertiliser creation involves two distinct pathways. After urine and fecal waste collection by Goldeimer, the liquid waste undergoes processing by VunaNexus in Eberswalde (County Barnim, Brandenburg) to produce liquid fertiliser, while Goldeimer manages solid waste in Ollsen (County Harburg, Lower Saxony) to produce compost (P2Green, 2025).

The following analysis considers both locations of the German pilot, respectively policies and strategies in Lower-Saxony and Berlin-Brandenburg on regional and federal state levels.

4.2. Stakeholders

The immediate stakeholders in the German pilot are

- Goldeimer: dry toilet service provider and operator for solid faecal matter composting.
- Vagtshoff: sustainable farming operator
- VunaNexus: technology provider for urine nutrient reclamation and fertiliser producer.
- Kreiswerke Barnim: facilitator for urine collection and treatment

Figure 13 Stakeholders of Germany's pilot project (P2GreenN, 2025)

Other *potential stakeholders* have also been identified. Actors who can play a role in the use of the technology (regulation, permits, planning) or dissemination (regulation, users, utilities), but also those who can help shape the attitudes of consumers/users (green, climate organizations, community or civil society organizations).

These are:

- National government
- Federal state governments in Berlin, Brandenburg and Lower Saxony
- County authorities and municipalities
- Regional planning authorities
- LEADER Action Groups and LEADER networks in the federal states
- Institutions supporting regional cooperation: Hamburg Metropolitan Region, Municipal Neighbourhood Fora
- Institutions supporting sustainable regional development: Regional parks, nature parks
- Universities, research centres

4.3. Governance levels in spatial context

Germany is a federal country with 16 federal states. Each of the federal states is differently organised internally, and a precise description cannot be presented here. There are 3 city-states (Berlin, Bremen, Hamburg) and 13 area-states (e.g. Brandenburg, Lower-Saxony). Most federal states have counties as an intermediate level, and all have the municipalities as a basic level (294 counties and 11,056 municipalities throughout Germany) (Bundesministerium des Inneren, 2025).

The German planning system follows the division and hierarchies embedded in the separation of powers at the federal, state and local levels, while adhering to the principle

of countervailing influence that requires coordination and adherence to higher-level rulings and designations (Turowski, 2002: 11). Table 2 shows the levels, tasks and various relationships between them for the two regions of the German pilot.

Table 4 The German Planning System (own, reproduced from Turowski 2002: 12)

State Level	Tiers of Planning	Legal Foundations	Planning Instruments		Function
Federation (Bund, national)	Spatial planning at Federal level	Spatial Planning Act	-		à principles of comprehensive spatial planning
Federal states (Länder)	Spatial planning at federal state level	Spatial planning Act and Land planning legislation	Comprehensive supra-sectoral plans	a Spatial structure plan	Aims of comprehensive spatial planning
	Regional planning			a special and sectoral sub-plans	
Municipalities	Urban land use planning	Federal building code	Urban land-use plans	a Preparatory land-use plan	Representation of land-use type
				a Local development plan	Designations of urban development

Generally speaking, both the strong instruments and the requirements for spatial planning and associated planning elements mostly fall to the states [Länder] with the federal level having some oversight and the duty to maintain consistency on a national planning level.

On the national level there is no comprehensive national spatial plan, but a policy document, the spatial planning act (Raumordnungsgesetz, ROG) that outlines key priorities, including competitiveness, sustainable land use, and climate adaptation. Additional sectoral plans, such as Landscape Plans, address environmental concerns. Furthermore, the Plan Notation Ordinance (Planzeichenverordnung, PlanZV) provides guidelines for the notation of plans.

On federal state level, Spatial Development Plans (Landesplanung) set broad strategies, while on regional level (defined differently in each federal state) Regional Plans (Regionalplanung) provide more detailed guidelines. While the federal government sets overarching laws, states can enact their own, with the most recent law taking precedence. This creates a system with broad similarities across states but significant variations in

details. The system follows a "counter-flow principle," balancing top-down and bottom-up decision-making and is guided by mutual feedback principle and subsidiarity.

Key federal laws governing spatial planning include the Federal Spatial Planning Act and the Federal Building Code, along with regulations affecting infrastructure and conservation. Coordination occurs through structured planning processes, ensuring lower-level plans align with higher-level strategies. The Basic Law protects property rights while allowing for expropriation for public good with compensation

On municipal level, the municipalities hold primary power over land-use planning through a two-tier system: Preparatory Land Use Plans outline development intentions, and Binding Land Use Plans determine specific land-use rights in accordance to land utilisation ordinance (Baunutzungsverordnung, BauNVO). If no Binding Plan exists, local authorities approve developments based on surrounding land use (Turowski, 2002; OECD, 2017)

4.4. Spatial Planning

a. Land Use Planning

Federal State Planning and Regional Planning in Berlin-Brandenburg

For the Berlin-Brandenburg part of the German pilot region, the joint federal state planning of Berlin and Brandenburg is relevant. The federal states Berlin and Brandenburg have decided to create a joint federal state planning institution (GL Gemeinsame Landesplanung Berlin-Brandenburg) which is unique in Germany, while all other federal states have their individual state planning. The core task of the joint Berlin-Brandenburg state planning (GL) is the development of the joint state development programme (LEPro) and joint state development plans (LEP Landesentwicklungspläne).

Like all spatial planning documents in Germany, also the joint state development plan Berlin-Brandenburg (LEP) contains objectives (Ziele) that are more binding and principles (Grundsätze) that are less binding.

The most important statements of the joint state development plan Berlin-Brandenburg (LEP) on agriculture are:

In Berlin-Brandenburg state planning, safeguarding the open space network is a state planning objective, but there is no objective for the preservation of agricultural land. Indirectly, however, agricultural land is also protected by safeguarding the open space network. The federal state planning has given the regional planning level (five regional planning communities in Brandenburg) the option of designating priority areas for agriculture (Vorranggebiet Landwirtschaft) which only the planning region of Havelland-Fläming opted for.

The following principles in the state development plan relate to agricultural issues:

Principle G 6.2: 'Agricultural land use is to be given special weight when weighing up competing utilisation claims. The further development of possibilities for the production of sustainable, organically produced agricultural products is of particular importance in addition to conventional production.'

Principle G 4.1 Cultural landscape action areas and G 4.2 Cultural landscape action concepts. The LEP proposes cultural landscape action areas in Berlin-Brandenburg. Action plans are to be drawn up for the development of the cultural landscape action areas.

The principles G 6.2, G 4.1, G 4.2 are not implemented by the state planning. In the case of G 6.2, funding instruments from agriculture policy are responsible. G 4.1 and G 4.2 are to be implemented by rural development stakeholders, in particular LEADER regions and local action groups (Gemeinsame Landesplanung Berlin-Brandenburg GL, 2021).

The most important statements of the joint state development plan Berlin-Brandenburg (LEP) on settlement development and open space preservation are that the focus of the settlement development is determined on the city of Berlin and its closer surrounding area, as well as in towns and larger villages (zentrale Orte) in Brandenburg to avoid urban sprawl in less densely populated areas. Vice versa settlement development is limited in rural areas and the LEP has the objective to prevent open spaces from settlement development (Gemeinsame Landesplanung Berlin-Brandenburg GL, 2021).

Regarding the regional planning in Berlin and Brandenburg, Brandenburg is divided into five planning regions (Havelland-Fläming, Lausitz-Spreewald, Oderland-Spree, Prignitz-Oberhavel, Uckermark-Barnim), see figure 13. A regional plan must be drawn up for each planning region, which concretises the spatial planning specifications from the state development programme and the state development plans. The regional plans are developed by the regional planning associations. Berlin as a city-state has its own regional and land-use plan, which will not be furtherly explained here.

Figure 14 Overview on the Planning Regions in Brandenburg (source: Gemeinsame Landesplanung GL Berlin-Brandenburg, 2025)

On the regional level, the regional plan (Regionalplan, Satzungsbeschluss Oktober 2024) of the planning region Uckermark-Barnim (Regional Planungsgemeinschaft Uckermark-Barnim) is relevant for the area of the pilot area.

The regional plan Uckermark-Barnim basically specifies on regional level the planning objectives and principles that are set in the state development plan for the whole of Berlin-Brandenburg as described above.

Most relevant is the principle to preserve open spaces for settlement development and to maintain the network of open spaces. The focus of settlement development shall be concentrated in the surrounding of Berlin and in town and villages that are declared as reserve areas (Vorbehaltsgebiet) for settlement development. Additionally, some areas are declared as reserve areas (Vorbehaltsgebiet) for tourism which is supported by the network of regional parks (see below).

The regional planning association addressed the problem of drought and water scarcity in the region. The study 'Analysis and evaluation of region-specific data on the landscape water balance in the Uckermark-Barnim planning region' (Analyse und Bewertung

regionalspezifischer Daten zum Landschaftswasserhaushalt der Planungsregion Uckermark-Barnim) that was commissioned by the regional planning association, states that the region is already one of the driest in Germany and will face growing drought periods. Therefore, the usage of groundwater for irrigation should be limited to stabilise the landscape water balance. As an alternative the study suggests using sufficiently purified (reclaimed) wastewater for irrigation in the future. At present this is only possible with temporary exemption authorisation. The irrigation with reclaimed water would support the restoration of groundwater. To exclude the entry of pollutants with the treated wastewater when it is used for irrigation, the existing limit values for pollutant levels should be complied and monitored (Regionale Planungsgemeinschaft Uckermark-Barnim, 2022).

Federal State Planning and Regional Planning in Lower Saxony

For the Lower Saxony part of the German pilot region, the federal state planning in Lower Saxony is relevant which is in the responsibility of Lower Saxony's Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Consumer Protection (Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft und Verbraucherschutz). The spatial plan for Lower Saxony is called State Spatial Planning Programme (LROP) 'Landes-Raumordnungsprogramm (LROP)'. Regarding the pilot activities, it contains objectives (Ziele) that are more binding, safeguarding the state of the open space network and protected areas (national parks, Natura 2000 areas), the protection of water bodies and groundwater. It also contains principles (Grundsätze) that are less binding like the preservation of agricultural land (ML, 2017).

Regarding regional planning in Lower Saxony the counties have the responsibility for the development of regional plans. The county of Harburg published in 2025 its regional plan 'Regionales Raumordnungsprogramm (RROP) 2025 für den Landkreis Harburg' (Landkreis Harburg, 2025a)

b. Environmental Planning

National level

Germany's National Strategy on Biological Diversity, adopted in 2007, sets visions, objectives, and over 400 measures for biodiversity conservation and sustainable use at national and global levels. It integrates environmental, economic, and social aspects in line with sustainability principles and is linked to Germany's National Sustainability Strategy and sectoral policies. Certain sites go through multi-level governance for protection in accordance with numerous national and international directives like the Wild Birds Directive (Directive 2009/147), Habitats Directive (Directives 92/43), and NATURA 2000 network (FAO, 2025).

State or Regional level

The Federal Ministry for the Environment initiated a broad dialogue and implementation process in 2007, involving governmental and non-governmental stakeholders. Since 2008, dialogue forums have engaged groups from nature conservation, business, science, social consciousness, and rural regions to discuss implementation strategies, build alliances, and set concrete action steps. A dedicated youth dialogue process and a major youth conference also addressed the younger generation.

The Federal States (*Länder*) play a key role in biodiversity conservation due to their responsibility for nature protection and landscape management. Many states have developed or are developing their own biodiversity strategies or action plans.

Figure 15 Spatial map Analysis. Source: (Daten LfU Bbg, 2024; MLUK,2023,edited by authors)

Municipal level

Additionally, a municipal alliance for biodiversity was established in 2012 to support local-level conservation efforts.

c. Circular Economy (Kreislaufwirtschaft) and climate action

In this section the strategies and plans for circular economy and climate action are presented together. The reason is that on federal state and regional level often no explicit circular economy strategies exists, but the topic is often included in the climate action plans.

The national circular economy strategy (Nationale Kreislaufstrategie) was published by the German government in 2024. Two measures are of relevance for the replication of the pilot solutions. Firstly 'Pilot actions 'Rural Circular Regions' and living labs' to test circular economy opportunities for rural areas. The German government has therefore launched the 'Rural Circular Regions' pilot action as part of the Territorial Agenda 2030 to support German model regions. In addition to spatial (further) development and implementation, circular economy concepts will also be promoted on a sector-specific basis in model 'real laboratory' approaches (BMUKN, 2024, p. 33). Secondly, the action 'Managing and recovering vital nutrients in regional cycles' including the support of solutions for recovery of nitrogen in wastewater treatment plants and phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge and sewage sludge ash (BMUKN, 2024, p. 39).

The actions in the circular economy strategy also refers to the objectives of the national bioeconomy strategy (Nationale Bioökonomiestrategie) that had been published in 2020 (BMBF, 2020).

Germany's Climate Action Plan 2050 was published by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB) in 2016.

Key measures include reducing nitrogen-based emissions from fertilizers, cutting methane emissions from ruminants, promoting organic farming to reach 20% of agricultural land, and utilizing EU agricultural policy funds to drive sustainable practices and emission reductions (BMUB, 2016).

Federal state level Berlin and Brandenburg

The Senate Department for the Environment, Transport and Climate Protection (Senatsverwaltung für Umwelt, Verkehr und Klimaschutz SenUVK) of Berlin adopted in 2021 the 'Waste management concept for municipal and construction waste as well as sewage sludge for the planning period 2020 to 2030 - Zero Waste Strategy of the State of Berlin' (Abfallwirtschaftskonzept für Siedlungs- und Bauabfälle sowie Klärschlämme für den Planungszeitraum 2020 bis 2030 – Zero Waste Strategie des Landes Berlin). (SenUVK , 2021). Regarding construction waste the strategy aims to support resource efficiency in construction. There are no measures listed regarding source separation or

closed water and nutrient cycles (SenUVK , 2021, p. 119). The strategy aims to recover more phosphorus from sewage sludge, however there are no measures listed to gain nutrients through source separation (SenUVK , 2021, p. 119).

For Brandenburg no separate circular economy strategy exists, the topic is covered by the climate action plan (MLUK, 2024).

The climate action plan Brandenburg (Klimaplan Brandenburg) was published in 2024 by Brandenburg's Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection (Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und Klimaschutz (MLUK)). The plan addresses eight fields of action for climate mitigation. The field of action 'Heat transition, construction and housing' addresses measures to support the sustainable construction and refurbishment of buildings, and the use of resource efficient materials. The field of action 'agriculture' addresses measures on the reduction of emissions caused by fertilisers, improved soil conservation and the reduction of energy demand of agriculture (MLUK, 2024). Although the measures do not explicitly address the topic of source separation and alternative fertilisers, the pilot solutions could be integrated in the realisation of the mentioned measures.

The Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection (MLUK) implements EU funding instruments for agri-environmental and climate measures while continually updating laws on plant protection, seed traffic, fertilizer use, and organic farming.

The administration prioritizes sustainable land management that aligns with both regional needs and EU environmental standards and acts as a legislative authority. Brandenburg is currently developing a bioeconomy strategy. To prepare the strategy the Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection (Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und Klimaschutz (MLUK)) conducted a participatory process and published a report on focal points for the future strategy. It contains the objectives to support the innovation in biomass cycles, and the establishment of living labs for innovative products and processes (DBFZ, n.d.). Based on the study, the bioeconomy is currently being developed by the newly formed Ministry of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Consumer Protection (Ministerium für Land- und Ernährungswirtschaft, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz MLEUV) which is the successor of the former MLUK (MLEUV, 2025). If the objectives that are mentioned in the study are transferred into measures in the strategy, they could offer opportunities to scale and replicate the pilot solutions.

For the federal state of Berlin, the Senate Department for Mobility, Transport, Climate Protection and Environment (Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt SenMVKU, equivalent to a state ministry) published in 2023 the Berlin Energy and Climate Protection Programme for the implementation period 2022 to 2026 (Berliner Energie- und Klimaschutzprogramm, Umsetzungszeitraum 2022 bis 2026). The programme addresses seven fields of action for climate mitigation. In the field 'buildings' the refurbishment of existing buildings and the sustainable construction of new buildings to avoid emissions are listed as measures to be supported. The topic of source separation

is not explicitly mentioned. Nevertheless, the measures in the programme could be used to support the implementation of the German pilot solution in the refurbishment of existing buildings or in new construction (SenMVKU, 2023, p. 44-51). The programme further addresses ten fields of action for climate adaptation. The field 'water' contains a measure on holistic water resource management. Although it does not contain the topic of source separation or black water cycles, the measure could be useful to support the implementation of the German pilot solution.

The topics of food production or of irrigation are not mentioned in the programme (SenMVKU, 2023)

The Senate Department for Justice and Consumer Protection (Senatsverwaltung für Justiz und Verbraucherschutz, SenJustV) developed a food strategy that does not contain measures regarding nutrient cycles of agricultural production. But it addresses regional food cycles in a broader sense (SenJustV, n.d.). This could be an entry point to place the topic of nutrient cycles and of the pilot solutions.

The federal state government of Berlin had allocated €28 million from the EU's Organic Farming Funding Program to support more farmers in transitioning to organic methods, underscoring the state's dedication to pesticide-free and environmentally friendly agriculture. The transition to organic is seen as essential for both environmental goals and Berlin's high demand for organic products (Ronzheimer, 2019).

Federal state level Lower Saxony

Lower Saxony has no separate circular economy strategy, but the climate mitigation strategy contains various aspects of circular economy.

The Lower Saxony Ministry for the Environment, Energy and Climate Mitigation (Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie und Klimaschutz MU) published in 2021 the Lower Saxony Climate Mitigation Strategy 2021 (Niedersächsische Klimaschutzstrategie 2021). It contains objectives and measures for seven sectors. For the sector 'buildings / urban development' (Gebäude / Stadtentwicklung) the focus is on reducing energy consumption. Some measures are more general. Measure 30 climate mitigation and village development (Klimaschutz und Dorfentwicklung) and measure 32 'internet platform climate mitigation in urban development' (Internetplattform "Klimaschutz in der Siedlungsentwicklung") could offer opportunities for the pilot solutions (MU, 2021, p 49). In the sector agriculture (Landwirtschaft) one focus is on fertilisers. Measure 43 , Implementation of the amended fertiliser law' (Umsetzung des novellierten Düngerechts) also focuses on good professional practice in the application of fertilisers and soil additives (MU, 2021, p 56). In the sector ,Land use, land use change, forestry'(Landnutzung, Landnutzungsänderung, Forstwirtschaft) measure 49 supports peat replacement and measure 52 supports carbon-farming models (MU, 2021, p. 69). Additionally, the strategy contains the cross-sectional measures. Measure 86 'The - Regions of the Future programme' (Program „Zukunftsregionen“) was launched in 2021 as a regional policy instrument. It supports counties to develop climate action measures together with different stakeholders (MU, 2021, p 87). The strategy furthermore financially

supports various measures on municipal level and offers support with the climate action agency KEAN (MU, 2021, p 100).

The Lower Saxony Ministry for the Environment, Energy and Climate Mitigation (Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie und Klimaschutz MU) just published in May 2025 the Lower Saxony Climate Mitigation Strategy 2025 (Niedersächsische Klimaschutzstrategie 2025). The new strategy contains the above-mentioned measures and continues their implementation (MU, 2025a, p. 142-144)

The county of Harburg published its integrated energy and climate mitigation concept in 2013. Like many earlier climate mitigation concepts, it focusses on energy and mobility topics and does not contain measures regarding agriculture, or nutrient cycles. (Landkreis Harburg, 2013). The county of Harburg supports agricultural businesses to reduce energy consumption (Landkreis Harburg, 2025b), but no further measures could be found regarding circularity in agriculture. A new climate action plan needs to be developed until 31.12.2025 following an obligation by the federal state Lower Saxony.

d. Water and sanitation planning

The responsibility for setting policies regarding sanitation in Germany is shared between the EU, the federal government and state governments. The municipalities are legally obliged to provide services and play an indirect role in influencing policy positions related to water and sanitation through their influential municipal associations.

Wastewater Charges Act (Abwasserabgabengesetz, AbwAG) regulates the payment of wastewater charges by parties liable for discharging wastewater into water bodies. Similarly, the Federal Water Act (Wasserhaushaltsgesetz, WHG) sets the overall framework for water management, including wastewater treatment and discharge while the Wastewater Ordinance (Abwasserverordnung, AbwV) implements the Federal Water Act and sets specific requirements for wastewater treatment, including limits for pollutants and monitoring values.

Surface Waters Ordinance (Oberflächengewässerverordnung, OGewV) and Groundwater Ordinance (Grundwasserverordnung, GrwV) regulate the protection of surface and groundwater, respectively. Additionally, Kreislaufwirtschafts- und Abfallgesetz (KrWG) or The Waste Management Act focuses on waste reduction, recycling, and disposal, including wastewater management.

The German National Water Strategy

The German National Water Strategy (Nationale Wasserstrategie) was developed by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, nukleare Sicherheit und Verbraucherschutz BMUV) and was adopted by the German government in 2023. It defines strategic topics and includes a water action programme with 78 actions. The most relevant actions for the pilots are: 'Action 41: Development of standardised nationwide

conceptual guidelines for the future design of water infrastructures' with the aim to develop guidelines to provide information on the consideration of climate resilience, resource conservation, sector coupling and multi-functionality in the design of infrastructure (BMUV, 2023, p. 97); 'Action 53: Develop 'guidance' on energy/water sector coupling' with the aim to support the energy/water sector coupling, to link the water, energy and waste management sectors and to optimise them in a joint holistic approach (BMUV, 2023, p. 102); 'Action 56: Promote the recovery of nutrients from wastewater and sewage sludge' aims to evaluate the Sewage Sludge Ordinance in particular with regard to the implementation of disposal concepts in municipalities and the promotion of innovative technologies for the recovery of phosphorus from sewage sludge and sewage sludge ash (BMUV, 2023, p. 103); and 'Action 71: Creation of a research and demonstration field for innovative water and wastewater technology' to support research on this topic (BMUV, 2023, p. 108). The actions are planned to be specified and implemented in different time frames.

Figure 16 Nutrient sensitive and affected areas in Brandenburg. (Source: Daten LfU Bbg, 2024, edited by Authors)

Berlin-Brandenburg joint water strategy.

The two federal states Berlin and Brandenburg announced that they will develop a first joint water strategy 'Wasserstrategie Hauptstadtregion 2050'. In 2023 the two federal state governments announced the strategy to be finalised end of 2024 (MLEUV, 2025). As of today, the joint strategy has not been published.

Figure 15 shows the nutrient sensitive and nitrate affected areas in Brandenburg. Large parts of the river basins of the rivers Havel and Oder are nutrient sensitive. The amount and size of nitrate affected areas are also significant.

Municipal wastewater systems in Brandenburg

The Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection in Brandenburg published in 2023 its latest report on municipal wastewater disposal in the State of Brandenburg (MLUK, 2023). According to the report, as of 31 December 2021, 88.9 percent of the population of Brandenburg - this corresponds to around 2.3 million inhabitants - are connected to a public sewage system which is connected to municipal wastewater treatment plants. The wastewater produced by 8.0% of the population is collected in drainless pits. This wastewater is collected through recurring collection and then properly disposed of at public sewage treatment plants. According to this, a total of 96.9% of the population of the state of Brandenburg has their wastewater treated in public wastewater treatment plants. 3.1% of the population - this corresponds to around 80,000 inhabitants - treat their wastewater in small sewage treatment plants (MLUK, 2023, p. 6).

The type of wastewater treatment in Brandenburg varies between urban and rural areas. The share of treatment in small sewage treatment plants in 2021 was very low in cities like Potsdam (0.3%), or Frankfurt an der Oder (0.1%) and in urbanized counties like Barnim (1%) or Potsdam-Mittelmark (1.2%) while it was very high in rural and peripheral counties like Spree-Neiße (14.4 %) and Prignitz (21.1 %) (MLUK, 2023, p. 18).

The Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection in Brandenburg highlights in its report that the decreasing population in rural areas will cause problems to the established wastewater system. Therefore, in rural areas in addition to the operation of small municipal wastewater treatment plants, the use of small sewage treatment plants and septic tanks cesspits can be an ecologically and economically sustainable sensible alternative. The ministry gives recommendations to the alternative solutions (MLUK, 2023, p. 19) but source separation is not mentioned as a solution in the report.

As shown in table 4 in 2021 all 60 WWTPs for more than 10,000 person equivalents, respectively all 9 plants for more than 100,000 person equivalents (p.e.) were equipped with N and P elimination in fulfilment of the minimum requirement of the EU Urban Wastewater Directive. In the group of smaller (<10,000 p.e.) most WWTPs are equipped, while in the group of very small WWTPs (<2,000 p.e.) the majority is not yet equipped (MLUK, 2023, p. 4-5).

In those WWTPs that have not yet been equipped, the Spanish pilot solution could be applied, if the reclaimed water is planned to be used for irrigation in the future. This is especially the case in peripheral counties and rural parts of counties.

Figure 17 Distribution of agricultural land and sewage treatment plants in Brandenburg. (Source: GDI- BBG, 2018, edited by authors)

Table 5 Status of the municipal wastewater treatment plants in Brandenburg according to treatment stage / nutrient reduction and size of the plant (own table, based on MLUK, 2023)

WWTP Type / size in population equivalents	>100,000	> 10,000 - 100,000	> 2,000 - 10,000	100 – 2000
Mechanical	0	0	0	0
Mechanical-biological	0	0	1	30
with N-Elimination	0	0	9	50
with P-Elimination	0	0	0	1
with N and P elimination	9	60	44	27

Lower Saxony water supply concept

Lower Saxony has published in 2022 its water supply concept (Wasserversorgungskonzept Niedersachsen). The concept estimates that the amount of groundwater to be used for irrigation in agriculture will grow while the use of groundwater by households and industry will stagnate (MU, 2022, p. 29). The concept does not explicitly recommend the usage of reclaimed water for irrigation in agriculture. However, the concept recommends considering the future use of reclaimed water for irrigation of woods to support the groundwater formation (MU, 2022, p. B13).

4.5. Spatial/Rural Development Support

Berlin and Brandenburg

In addition to its formal planning instruments, the Joint regional planning organisation of Berlin-Brandenburg (GL) provides financial support for informal instruments and projects. The most important examples are the Municipal Neighbourhood Forums KNF and the umbrella organisation Regional Parks as well as the seven individual regional parks. Both the KNF and the regional parks have a role to play in promoting inter-municipal cooperation and regional development. While the KNF were established to enhance cooperation between city-districts in Berlin and counties / municipalities in Brandenburg and have so far focussed primarily on the development axes from Berlin to the surrounding areas of Brandenburg (the so-called settlement star), the regional parks are dedicated to the areas between the settlement axes and to prevent open spaces from urban development. The Municipal Neighbourhood Forums KNF and regional parks work in a division of labour, so to speak. Examples of more recent projects and developments include the creation of the Green Masterplan (with the aim of qualifying the regional parks), KNF projects to strengthen inner city development and the cross-state compensation management project.

On the smaller pilot region scale the relevant actors are the municipal neighbourhood forum North (KNF Nord) and the Naturpark Barnim. The Naturpark Barnim developed a climate mitigation masterplan which contains various potential bioeconomy measures (e.g. usage of agricultural organic waste for energy production) that could be connected to the activities of the German pilot. The masterplan also mentions the dry toilets that are tested by Barnim county as a good example (Naturpark Barnim, 2021).

Rural development in Brandenburg is supported by the 14 LEADER regions that are coordinated in the Brandenburg's State Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection (Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und Klimaschutz MLUK) With support from European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) initiatives are promoted in particular to counteract the consequences of demographic change, to support and sustainably implement job-creating development projects and to secure basic services in rural areas. There are many projects in the individual regions that promote regional marketing and support regional production chains (MLUK, 2022). On the smaller pilot region scale the relevant actor is the LEADER group of Barnim county which supported

several projects including the refurbishment and construction of buildings for commercial and cultural use, the support of regional businesses and tourism (LAG Barnim, 2025).

Lower Saxony

There are several institutions that support or influence the regional development in the pilot area of Lower Saxony.

The Hamburg Metropolitan Region MRH (Metropolregion Hamburg) is centred around the city of Hamburg in northern Germany; it supports regional cooperation and projects with its development funds. Furthermore, it supports networking and knowledge exchange in the form of working groups (MRH, 2025).

The Süderelbe AG is a public-private cooperation to support the economic development of the region south of Hamburg. It supports projects one of which is the initiatives to develop a model cradle-to-cradle region (Süderelbe AG, 2025).

Nature parks and biosphere reserves are areas that aim to protect preserved areas and at the same time support sustainable tourism and regional development. The pilot area is located in the nature park Lüneburger Heath (Naturpark Lüneburger Heide). In some distance to the pilot area are further biosphere reserves (Biosphärenreservat) ‚Niedersächsische Elbtalau‘, and the nature parks Elbhöhen-Wendland and Südheide. They all support sustainable agriculture and tourism (MU, 2025b). A topic is the provision of toilets for visitor centres and other touristic infrastructure in remote areas for which the pilots could offer solutions.

LEADER is organised in Lower Saxony in cooperation with the federal states of Bremen and Hamburg in the joint program KLARA (Klima, Landwirtschaft, Artenvielfalt, Regionale Akteur:innen). There are several LEADER regions in the area of the pilot ‚Naturpark Lüneburger Heide‘, and in the larger region ‚Achter-Elbe-Diek‘, ‚Regionalpark Rosengarten‘, ‚Heideregion Uelzen‘, ‚Elbtalau‘ that fund projects for rural development and could support the replication of the pilot (KLARA, 2025).

4.6. Policies and Regulations

Fertilisers derived from human excreta

Current regulations in Germany lack specific legal frameworks for utilizing products derived from human excreta or even just urine. The products can only be used under exceptional circumstances like research or as secondary resources in line with recycling legislation (Source: DWA, n.d.).

The approval of a new fertilizer is applied at the Federal Agricultural Ministry „Bundesministerium für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft und Verbraucherschutz (BMELV)“ based on the technical evaluation and recommendation of a scientific advisory

board. The Fertilizer Act (DüNG) emphasizes crop nutrition, soil fertility, human and animal health, and environmental safety, focusing on nutrient efficiency and EU law alignment.

The Fertilizer Regulation (DüMV) controls market placement, monitored through the official Fertilizer Transport Controls (DVK) to ensure compliance. It sets best practices for fertilizer application, including determining needs, timing, and environmental protection (e.g., buffer zones for waterways and ammonia emission reduction).

Limits on heavy metal inputs in Germany are governed by the fertilizer regulations (DüMV) and waste management regulations (BioAbfV, AbfKlärV).

The Wirtschaftsdüngerverbringungsverordnung (WDüNGV) (manure transfer regulation) governs placing on the market, transport and taking possession of manure, as well as the related commercial substance streams.

Bundes-Bodenschutz- und Altlastenverordnung (BBodSchV) (soil protection regulation) as well as the Law on Food and Feed (LFGB) lay down limit values for pollutants and heavy metals (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2021).

4.7. Spatial Analysis and Recommendations

Use of reclaimed water in areas with drought problems

At moment the use of reclaimed water for irrigation in agriculture is rare in Germany. However, it could become more important in areas that are facing increasing droughts. In Brandenburg the use for agriculture is already being discussed, in Lower Saxony the focus is on reusing reclaimed water for irrigation of woods.

For the majority of WWTPs in Germany that are already equipped with N&P recovery the Spanish pilot solution cannot be applied in its initial concept. Nevertheless, the remote nutrition monitoring might be also useful for irrigation with reclaimed water from WWTPs with N&P recovery to control the amount of nutrients.

Smaller WWTPs without N&P recovery that are mainly present in rural areas could be equipped with the Spanish pilot solution to use the reclaimed water for irrigation and control the amount of nutrients. This could economise investment for N&P recovery in small WWTPs that are difficult to finance in areas with a decreasing population.

Possible financial support for the implementation of the pilot solutions should be envisaged. Although the water strategies of Germany and the federal states do not directly mention incentives for implementing solutions for irrigation with reclaimed water or decentralised sanitation systems, they highlight the problematic of high costs of

conventional solutions and the risks of water scarcity. Therefore, funding for the replication of the pilot solutions might become possible in the future.

Decentralised sanitation systems for rural areas and touristic infrastructure

Germany's existing centralized sewer systems require substantial refurbishment. According to a study, an estimated cost of €5.85 billion is required to cover the costs over a period of 30 years (Aus Der Beek et al., 2022).

In many rural areas the sanitation systems need to be modernised in the next decades. For example, there are over 5.000 non-connected households in the county of Barnim.

For rural areas that are facing a decline in population the implementation of decentralised sanitation systems with source-separation should be supported as an alternative to just renewing conventional decentralised solutions (small sewage treatment plants, septic tanks cesspits) or to huge investments to connect to larger centralised sewage systems.

Decentralised sanitation systems with source-separation are already installed in some touristic infrastructures like visitor centres. This should be replicated in other touristic areas especially in regional and nature parks and nitrate vulnerable or even effected areas. The replication could be supported by the regional and nature park administrations or by local LEADER initiatives. Source-separation in touristic infrastructures should be as well used for educative purposes and work as good example for the transfer to other buildings in rural areas.

Source-separation and decentralised sanitation in urban areas – potential of new developments, refurbishment of existing buildings and of public toilets

In urban areas source-separation and decentralised sanitation should be supported in new development projects and the refurbishment of existing buildings. Therefore, strategies and concepts that support sustainable and circular construction should be adapted to include these solutions. There is a high demand for more public toilets in many cities, source-separation and decentralised sanitation solutions should be supported as a sustainable and cost-effective alternative to conventional public toilets.

Institutions and programs of spatial development as supporters and multipliers

Institutions that influence spatial development should be reached to convince them of the positive effects of the pilot solutions and win them as supporters. Most important institutions are LEADER groups for rural areas, nature and regional parks, inter-municipal cooperation structures, and metropolitan regions for larger scale cooperation.

5. Conclusions

The aim of this analysis was to present the *spatial and territorial planning aspects* of the investigated innovative source-separation respectively wastewater-based nutrient

utilization technologies. The report examined the applicability of 4 different pilot technologies in 3 different case study regions.

As a summary can be collected the *main territorial aspects* of the investigated innovative technologies:

Table 6 Comparison table of spatial dimensions of investigated technologies (Edited by Authors)

Use cases	Swedish urine collection, dried pellets	Spanish reclaimed WW, irrigation	German dry toilet, composting	German urine collection, liquid fertilizer
Territorial scale of nutrient collection	Regional (economies of scale)	Local (WWT area)	Regional (economies of scale)	Regional (economies of scale)
Territorial scope of nutrient based end product	Usable anywhere	Locally usable (pipeline is needed)	Locally usable (short transport distance required)	Usable anywhere
Territorial thinking of regulatory framework	Local/regional water protection rules	Territorial irrigation/water protection rules	Local/regional water protection and waste treatment rules	Territorial water protection rules
Spatial scale of regulatory actors	National	National/Regional	National	National
Spatial extent of the necessary partnership	Local/Regional	Local/Regional	Local/Regional	Local/Regional

It can be stated that the **following general spatial and planning aspects need to be analysed** in the case of a given replication effort. These are the following:

- Governance levels and roles,
- Regulation background,
- Land use planning rules,
- Development planning practice,
- Partnerships making methods.

It is necessary to explore the *territorial governance* structure of the region where the given technology potentially will be installed. Which governance actors have what functions, powers and room for manoeuvre.

What is the *regulatory background*, what technological limitations are in force in the investigated region (e.g. water protection, possibility of using artificial fertilizers, nitrate sensitivity, etc.). It is important here to collect the rules for both the production and use of the fertilizer. The determining element of the regulation is the analysis of the restrictions and permits designated by the *land use plans*. All this helps in selecting the appropriate technology and in designating a suitable site or application area for technology replicators.

The *development directions* of the target/replicator regions (whether they appear in development plans, action plans, or specific development programs and projects) can be a decisive connection point during the deployment of the innovative technologies presented here. The technologies examined in this report reflect different regional challenges, so their successful adaptation presupposes the application of replicator regions with similar challenges. Regional planning documents, whether sectoral or complex plans, usually respond to these identified regional challenges, so they can be good starting points for identifying the problem and selecting suitable technological solutions.

For successful adaptation, it is essential for the technology replicator to *identify, select and involve appropriate* regional partners in the planning and preparation processes, as this can be the guarantee of successful joint implementation.

Based on the analysis of use cases, **the following main steps can be identified for a potential replication process:**

1. Identification of the problem area;
2. Delimitation of the intervention area (replication region);
3. Selection of (all) possible technologies and solutions;
4. Review of relevant regulatory elements (for all potential solutions);
5. Analysis of the connection to sectoral development and regional development challenges and objectives;
6. Selecting technology that fits local characteristics (alternative analysis);
7. Identification of potential partners;
8. Setting partners' objectives (indicators) and
9. Fixing a timetable for implementation (permits, funding, construction, etc.).

The case study descriptions, and the summary findings are partly based on literature reviews and (planning, regulating, etc.) document analyses, but most importantly on interviews and workshops with stakeholders of the investigated regions. Based on this, it can be noted that the *most important conditions for successful replication are local (space-based) knowledge, knowledge of the technologies to be applied and continuous dialogue with all potential stakeholders.*

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